

EVALUATION OF BENDING FATIGUE CHARACTERISTICS OF CFRP FOR SHIP PROPELLERS

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ABSTRACT

The bending fracture behaviour of quasi-isotropic CFRP manufactured from vacuum assisted resin transfer molding (VaRTM) process with multi-axial stitched fabrics were investigated by 3-point bending tests to evaluate its applicability to marine propellers. VaRTM process is attractive in terms of saving costs and manufacturing a large product effectively. Through the tests, some differences of fatigue characteristics between the number of cycles were observed. When bending rigidity under the fatigue condition was focused from the view of increase of bending deflection of the specimen, stiffness degradation was evaluated at different stages among the number of the cycles. It indicates stiffness is not strongly associated with bending deflection. About fracture appearance, the fibre breakage was observed both under low cycle loading and high cycle loading in the same part of the specimen. Similar fracture was observed regardless of the number of the cycles. From these observations, it is speculated that bending rigidity has a strongly correlation with the crack extension.

1 INTRODUCTION

Recently, an alternative material for marine propellers instead of the conventional nickel aluminium bronze (NAB) is strongly needed due to a rise in the price of copper and a request to reduce the environmental burden of ships. Considering the decrease in environmental burden of ships, it is one of critical solutions to improve propeller performance [1-2, 7]. Carbon fibre reinforced plastics (CFRP) are assumed that they are suitable for improving performance of marine propellers due to high fatigue strength, and is expected as the alternative material. They also have advantages for marine propellers including lightweight and corrosion resistance [1-2, 7].

When considering the loading condition in marine propellers, bending force is the major one. Thus it is strongly needed to validate bending strength and fracture behaviour of materials for the application to marine propellers. However, little is known about these bending fatigue characteristics of CFRP for marine propellers. Especially, few studies focused on the bending fatigue behaviour during more than 10^7 load cycles. Because in operation, 2.0×10^8 cyclic loads act on marine propellers in inspection period, it is therefore desirable to predict fatigue strength and fracture behaviour at high cycles.

For manufacturing structural composites components in aerospace applications, autoclave curing process is commonly used. CFRP manufactured from autoclave curing process has high strength, while the process needs large-scale equipment and high cost [3]. About the methods of fabricating CFRP, there is also the vacuum assisted resin transfer molding (VaRTM) process. VaRTM is attractive in terms of saving costs and manufacturing a large product effectively [4]. Thus in this study, the focus lies on the vacuum assisted resin transfer molding (VaRTM) process for the application to marine propellers.

About fatigue behaviour, in this study we especially focus on considering influence of the loading cycles and displacement on stiffness degradation during the fatigue condition. As rigidity is critical

component in the performance of propeller, difference of stiffness degradation due to variation in loading cycles is evaluated as first step to validate proper failure criterion about bending fatigue.

Moreover, here we examine about fatigue damage of the specimens by observing cross-section surface to verify whether there are differences among loading cycle magnitude.

2 EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

2.1 Materials

In order to evaluate bending strength of CFRP for the marine propellers, we especially used CF/EP, which is a carbon fibre reinforced epoxy, because it is assumed that epoxy shows better performances in terms of mechanical properties and resistance to environmental degradation. The material used was fabric T-700. Laminate was made by “Non Crimp Fabric (NCF)”. Layers of NCF are typically stitch bonded with a polyester thread to form a fabric. Because the straight fibres within NCF composites allow good resin penetration and is hard to be distorted [5], NCF composite can be suitable for propeller. The specimens in this study were laminated 8 piles. The stacking configurations of each laminate were [0/90] and [+45/-45]. By stacking these laminates in turns, the specimens had quasi-isotropic properties. The stacking configuration of [(+45/-45)/(90/0)/(-45/+45)/(0/90)]_s was prepared for the specimen. The stacking configurations of specimens were symmetric to prevent them from distorting because of differences in each lamina’s stiffness.

2.2 Bending Fatigue Test

To examine bending fatigue strength of the specimens manufactured from VaRTM process, and to evaluate the damage in the specimens, 3-point bending fatigue tests were carried out using fatigue test machines (Instron 8800 servohydraulic test systems or Shimadzu servopulser). The bending fatigue strength tests were conducted being based on JIS K-7074, the standard of static bending tests of CFRP [8]. Figures 1 and 2 show a picture and a schematic drawing of the bending fatigue test. All specimens were the same size; the width, b , was 15 mm, the length, l , was 114 mm, and the thickness, h , was 3 mm. All tests were subjected to the same regulation of 3-point bending for this test method. The specimen size was also based on this standard. Span length of this test was 96 mm. Cyclic tests were carried out under load control at stress ratios, R , of 0.1 at room temperature. The loading form was a sine wave, and these tests were conducted in cycling frequency of 5 Hz. These test conditions were decided considering the operation environment of a marine propeller.

In the tests, a number of cycles and the maximum displacement were recorded. Displacement was recorded at the level of crosshead of the device, which lay in contact with the centre of the specimen. In this report, N stands for a number of cycles in the fatigue test. We defined the displacement at $N = 300$ as an initial value.

The fracture bending stress equation is as following, written in this JIS standard:

$$\sigma = \frac{3PL}{2bh^2} \quad (1)$$

where σ is the bending stress (MPa), P is the maximum loading at fracture (N), L is the span length (mm), b is the width of the specimen (mm), and h is the thickness of the specimen (mm).

2.3 The calculation of stiffness

In this experiment, in addition to the loads and the maximum displacement when the specimen fractured, the transition of loads and displacement on specific cycles were recorded. We regarded specific cycles when the displacement of the crosshead reached $1.00 \times 0.05n$ ($n = 1, 2, 3 \dots$) times than the initial value ($N = 300$). We obtained 200 data of a set of load and displacement from each specific cycle and calculated the stiffness from them. The fatigue test was continued until the displacement reached twice than default to evaluate stiffness degradation and differences of crack propagation under this condition and decide the proper failure criterion.

Flexural rigidity of each cycle is calculated by following equation,

$$EI(N) = \frac{L^3}{48} \left(\frac{\Delta P}{\Delta \delta} \right) \quad (2)$$

where EI is flexural rigidity ($N \cdot mm^2$) and δ is displacement of crosshead (mm). Flexural rigidity is calculated with an approximation of $\Delta P / \Delta \delta$ from load-displacement chart.

Figure 1 Bending fatigue test

Figure 2 Schematic drawing of bending test

3 EXPERIMENTAL RESULT

3.1 Stiffness degradation of LCF and HCF

There are two commonly recognized forms of fatigue about cycles: low-cycles fatigue (LCF), which is damage that is related to stress cycles that lead to component failure in less than 10,000 cycles, and high-cycles fatigue (HCF), in more than 10,000 cycles. Regarding marine propellers, the expected amount of cycles in operation is more than 10^8 . It is important to examine characteristics of fatigue fracture, especially for HCF loading.

Figure 3 shows typical examples of time variations of stiffness and the displacement of the specimen about LCF at the stress ratio 0.1. Stiffness decreases gradually in the single logarithmic chart from the start of the test ($N = 300$). Stiffness degradation is linear until the order of 10^4 , but rigidity declines drastically when it reaches 90% of the initial value. When the displacement reaches 1.2 times than initial, rigidity of the specimen is about 85%, which is almost in agreement with the theoretical value of 83.3%.

Stiffness degradation under HCF loading is indicated in Figure 4. In the same manner as LCF, it declines gradually in the single logarithmic chart in first phase of HCF loading. In this chart, it declines drastically around 85% of initial value. When the displacement reaches twice the default: the test breaks, stiffness produces a marked drop in 73% of default. Figure 4 also shows the increase in displacement of the specimen. When the displacement reaches 1.2 times displacement, stiffness is still around 90% of the initial value.

From these two charts, some difference in stiffness degradation and displacement increase between LCF and HCF were observed. Focusing attention on the stiffness when the displacement increased 1.2 times than the initial value, flexural rigidity resulted in an enough drop for LCF loading. On the other hand, for HCF loading the specimen still kept high rigidity in this situation. It indicates when we focus on this fatigue behaviour from the view of displacement increase, we evaluate stiffness degradation of the specimen at different stages between LCF and HCF. It indicates bending stiffness degradation is not strongly associated with bending deflection under fatigue condition.

3.2 Fracture observation of the specimen

To compare bending fatigue behaviour between LCF and HCF, fatigue crack propagation was investigated. In this research, after surfaces of the specimens were polished by sandpaper 400 and 800 grit, cross-section surface of the specimen, in which stacking and fracture of each layer were looked easily, was observed by a digital microscope (KEYENCE VHX-1000).

Figure 5 shows a typical cross-section surface in the region of LCF at the stress ratio 0.1. 0° layer stands for the longitudinal direction of the specimen, and this layer looks like a white line. In the figure, compressive stress is applied to the upper part, and tensile stress to the lower part. Generally, damage develops first in the matrix of the piles in the transverse direction to the applied load which extends in the matrix of the piles parallel to the applied load with increasing number of cycles, and local delamination and interfacial between fibre and matrix damage are developed [6]. It seems that some cracks are observed in both compressive and tensile directions. On the tensile surface, there are some transverse cracks in 90° or 45° piles and delamination especially between 90° and 45° ply. On the compressive surface, in addition to these cracks, fibre bundles breakage in 0° ply is observed. It implies the specimen is completely fractured during LCF loading.

Typical damage of the specimen in the region of HCF is shown in Figure 6. In the figure, there are some transverse cracks and delamination in both compressive and tensile area in the same manner as that for LCF loading. In the 0 ply, fibre buckles breakage is also observed in the compressive area.

On the other hand, about the specimen under HCF loading whose test was stopped when the displacement reached 1.2 times than default value, some different fracture observation were confirmed. Figure 7 shows typical cross-section surface of the specimen under this situation. In the same manner as LCF, there are some transverse cracks and delamination in tensile directions. However, No cracks are observed on the compressive surface. As for fibre bundles breakage, there is no fracture in the specimen. It indicates the specimen does not fail perfectly for HCF loading with the failure criterion about increase in the displacement. It is speculated that not bending deflection but bending stiffness has a strongly correlation with the crack extension. It is possible that the crack extension of CFRP can be grasped by measuring bending rigidity under fatigue condition.

Figure 3 Stiffness degradation and displacement accession for LCF loading

Figure 4 Stiffness degradation and displacement accession for HCF loading

Figure 5 Cross-section surface for LCF loading

Figure 6 Cross-section surface for HCF loading

Figure 7 Cross-section surface for HCF loading with the criterion “1.2 times displacement”

4 CONCLUSIONS

The bending fatigue characteristics of carbon/epoxy composite manufactured from VaRTM (vacuum assisted resin transfer molding) process were investigated to validate fatigue behaviour for LCF and HCF loading and show the direction of the road ahead establishing a proper failure criterion, for it will be contributory to evaluate whether CFRP could be applied to marine propellers.

In this paper, flexural rigidity degradation during fatigue test under LCF and HCF loading was investigated. In both cases, similar degradation was observed. As the same time of drastic drop of stiffness, sharp increase of displacement was confirmed. Under LCF loading, when the displacement of specimen reached 1.2 times than default value, flexural rigidity resulted in an enough drop. On the other hand, under HCF loading specimen still had high rigidity. It implies that bending stiffness degradation is evaluated at different stage between LCF and HCF from the view of displacement increase.

About fracture appearance, similar fracture was observed regardless of the number of the cycles. The fibre breakage was observed both under low cycle loading and high cycle loading. It is presumed that the fracture characteristics are similar from the view of the number of cycle, and bending rigidity has a strongly correlation with the crack extension. If the function of marine propellers is strongly influenced by crack extension of CFRP, the failure criterion should be considered about crack propagation. In this case, it speculates that it is effective to establish the fatigue failure criterion using bending stiffness as a primary measure.

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